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PHOENIX

Nanomedicine for organ transplant tolerance

Initial Communication, Dissemination & Exploitation plan

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PHOENIX Consortium

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1. Executive Summary

Strategic communication, dissemination and exploitation will help explain the wider societal relevance of our new science, build support for future research and innovation funding, ensure uptake of our results within the scientific community, and open up potential business opportunities for our novel therapeutics and services. Overall, it will help increase the impact of PHOENIX research and innovation.

In the PHOENIX project, our consortium will develop and validate a new immunotherapy for transplant medicine that prevents graft rejection and induces transplant tolerance, without compromising normal immunity to infections and cancer.

PHOENIX aims to pre-clinically validate this new approach in transplants of two organs (kidney and liver) in two animal species (mice and pigs), to provide robust evidence for future clinical trials.

In this project, Work Package 5 *Communications, Dissemination, Exploitation and Management* (WP5) is led by two beneficiaries, Istituto di Ricerche Farmacologiche Mario Negri (IRFMN) and Pintail Limited (PT), and has four objectives:

1. To orchestrate and facilitate the progress of the project and all work packages and activities
2. To promote the aims and activities of the project (communication) and of its results (dissemination)
3. To identify, manage and protect new intellectual property and innovation
4. To prepare for the further development and exploitation of the project results.

The topic of this report is Deliverable 5.2 *Initial Communications, Dissemination and Exploitation Plan* (D5.2) (the Initial Plan) for which PT is the lead beneficiary. D5.2 is an output of the following tasks, noting that these tasks span the duration of the project. This Initial Plan will be updated in Month 18 via Deliverable 5.4 *Updated Communications, Dissemination and Exploitation Plan*.

- Task 5.2 – Communication
- Task 5.3 – Dissemination
- Task 5.4 – Innovation Management
- Task 5.5 - Exploitation Planning

Effective communication, dissemination and exploitation relies upon contributions from all partners to raise the profile, mission and results of the project. This entails communicating with the general public and other researchers, as well as networking and partnering with projects and institutions in related fields.

Communication of the PHOENIX project and its results will engage the public, media, and wider society, in addition to the scientific, clinical, and patient communities. Messaging will concern the project itself (*activities*) and its results (*novel concepts*) and will emphasise the benefits of research to society, using accessible, non-specialist language.

Dissemination of results will target specific stakeholders that can use our results in their own work, and that are important in our longer-term exploitation plans: this includes the scientific and industrial research communities, clinical societies and transplant physicians, patients and their representative organisations, healthcare providers and funders. Dissemination will make extensive use of open science repositories and processes, while respecting our innovation and exploitation plans.

D5.2 Initial Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation Plan

Through communication and dissemination, we aim to achieve the following:

- attract the best experts to our team
- share best practices with others
- promote our researchers' activities and results
- trigger new collaborations and opportunities
- generate market demand for the goods and services we are working to develop
- raise citizens' awareness of how their public money is being spent, and
- demonstrate the success of European collaboration.

Exploitation and further development planning will prepare for the next steps toward clinical trials.

This report outlines the approach taken to develop the Initial Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation Plan (the Initial Plan) and the results, being the Initial Plan itself.

2. Introduction and Background

Organ transplant medicine is currently limited by life-long immunosuppression and vulnerability to infections, malignancies and cardiovascular diseases. Further, there is a 20% rate of long-term graft failure. The PHOENIX project addresses this challenge, by reprogramming the local immune micro-environment around a graft organ, inducing long-term transplant tolerance without broader systemic immunosuppression.

In PHOENIX, the team are designing and building a unique nanomedicine which delivers ubiquitous or self-antigens - common to all humans – that will redirect the host immune response against the graft toward regulation and tolerance development. These medicines will be demonstrated in murine and porcine models, laying the foundation for human clinical trials immediately post-project.

PHOENIX as a project aligns to Horizon Europe *Destination 3 of the Health Work Programme* in that it tackles disease to reduce disease burden. Notably, it makes a substantial contribution to effectively reducing the disease burden on patients due to a better understanding and treatment of diseases, and more effective and innovative health technologies.

It is expected that the PHOENIX nano-therapy will have a transformative effect, reducing the disease burden on the target group, being organ transplant patients. Grafts will survive long-term, eliminating the need for second transplants and reducing waiting times for new transplant patients. Patients will no longer need life-long immunosuppression, avoiding its toxicity, and will live longer with higher quality of life. This is underpinned thanks to our more effective and innovative health technologies – in this case the nano-immunotherapy delivered by PHOENIX.

The *communication, dissemination and exploitation* of PHOENIX will be key to these expectations being met. In this regard, WP5 cuts across all other work packages in the project and is central to the overall success of the project (see Figure 1). Led by partners IRFMN and PT, WP5 activities will also be supported and informed by the other two PHOENIX beneficiaries (FCRB and CHUR).

WP5 has four main objectives, as outlined above, with the second (*to promote the aims and activities of the project (communication) and its results (dissemination)*), the third (*to identify, manage and*

protect new intellectual property and innovation), and fourth objectives (to prepare for the further development and exploitation of the project results) being relevant to this deliverable report (D5.1).

Figure 1 – PHOENIX Work Package Structure

3. Approach

Project outputs will become available throughout the course of PHOENIX, therefore it is essential to closely capture, monitor and manage results, (taking into consideration IP protection) over the lifetime of the project and adjust communication activities, as well as dissemination and exploitation plans accordingly.

Due to the nature of the PHOENIX research, only a small selection of the deliverable reports (D5.1 Website, D5.2 Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation Plan, D5.3 Initial Data Management Plan, D5.4 Updated Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation (CDE) Plan, and D5.5 Updated Data Management Plan) will be made public, thus the outward facing activities as outlined in this Initial Plan will be the core publicly available information about the project. We plan to review and update the Data Management Plan (D5.5 due month 18) as necessary and/or with the periodic reports.

In this section, the approach and considerations taken in the development of the Initial Plan are outlined, starting with the target audiences and key messages, and project branding and logo, communications and dissemination toolkit and then progressing through the three topics of communication, dissemination, and exploitation.

To ensure that the Initial Plan is informed by the views, networks, expertise and needs of the project beneficiaries, an online consultation survey (see Appendix A) to gain their insights was conducted by WP5.

3.1 Target Audiences, Communication Channels and Key Messages

Communication, dissemination, and exploitation activities in PHOENIX, including the key messages and channels utilised, have been tailored to reach and engage specific target audiences.

Our most important audiences are the general public, patients and their representative advocacy organisations, the academic and industrial research communities, transplant clinicians, and those industry sectors which could play a role in commercialisation and exploitation of PHOENIX.

As a consortium, we co-created tailored messages and will design the associated materials for each target audience, emphasising those aspects of PHOENIX and its impact that are most important to that audience. The public will be informed about exciting new science and the value of publicly funded research, for example, while clinicians will learn about important new tools to improve patient care and outcomes.

Each audience will receive its messaging via specific activities and channels, selected to best reach that audience. The research communities will thus be reached via publications and conferences, the public via our website and social media, plus the mass media (noting that in line with Article 17.1, before engaging in a communication or dissemination activity expected to have a major media impact, we will inform the granting authority).

PHOENIX partners have connections to other researchers and project teams to stimulate further research both through face-to-face networking at conferences, training events, and in-house institutional seminars and digitally through social media and web links. We plan to leverage our networks in order to maximise the reach of our work in the communication and dissemination domains.

In addition to the target audiences and key messages outlined in the Grant Agreement (as per above), WP5 consulted (the online survey) further with all four beneficiaries to refine the list of target audiences and the key messages to be used in this Initial Plan. Consortium members understand that as the project progresses, the target audiences and messages can be further refined, noting this would be reflected in the Updated Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation Plan (D5.4) in Month 18.

3.2 Branding, Logo and Website

PHOENIX, through Deliverable 5.1 – *Project Website* (D5.1), has already established a strong brand identity, including a logo, colour scheme, standardised templates for slide decks, minutes, agendas, and reports. The EU acknowledgement, disclaimer and logo have been built into each of these products.

The PHOENIX website (<https://www.phoenix-he.eu/>) was launched on 18 May 2023. The website includes descriptions of the project concept, the team involved, and will include results achieved, key innovations, benefits for patients, hospitals and other stakeholders, and societal impact (to be updated throughout the project). The project website will be a key channel, linked to social media, through which contact with the project and its partners can be made.

3.3 Communication and Dissemination Toolkit

In line with the branding and logo, a communication and dissemination toolkit for use across communication and dissemination activities by all beneficiaries will be developed. This will include as per the Grant Agreement, professional illustrations, videos, and animations explaining the project and results.

All beneficiaries via the consultation survey had the opportunity to identify additional products that would be of value to them in the communication and dissemination toolkit.

3.4 Leveraging beneficiary networks

The PHOENIX team collectively boast extensive expertise and reputations in their respective scientific fields. The networks of this team will be leveraged for the benefit of communication, dissemination and exploitation activities related to the PHOENIX project.

Further, the expertise of team members as leaders in their scientific fields will be built into communication activities, via for example a Social Media series presenting the team.

Opportunities to leverage the beneficiaries' networks will be explored through the consultation survey.

3.5 Interaction with Sister and Related Projects

PHOENIX positively views the opportunity to cooperate with 'like' EU-funded projects, identifying potential synergies. The sister projects, funded under this 'next generation immunotherapies' topic will be contacted to explore where synergy and collaboration opportunities exist.

Related EU-funded research projects in which our partners are involved have been described and linked to on the website's new Related Research page, <https://www.phoenix-he.eu/what-is-phoenix/related-projects/>.

3.6 Communication

The communication of PHOENIX is outlined in Task 5.2 – *Communication*, of the Grant Agreement and spans the duration of the project.

Processes to ensure the smooth flow of internal communication in PHOENIX were put in place. A project email circulation list was established for intra-project communication. Dropbox is used to share, collaborate on and review reports and documents. A monthly teleconference schedule was drawn up. These meetings will take place via Zoom on the last Friday of each month. Minutes will be taken, circulated for review and amendment, if necessary, and then federated and stored in Dropbox for future reference.

A press release detailing the project mission, aims, partners and funding was drafted by PT and circulated for input and tailoring to partner institutions. It was issued by coordinating institution, IRFMN on May 17, 2023. The news was echoed by European traditional media organisations and shared widely on social media platforms LinkedIn, Facebook, Twitter and Instagram. The details of this activity are catalogued in the PHOENIX Dissemination Register. With additional news-worthy findings emanating from PHOENIX, it is envisaged that the same process will occur.

As articulated in the Grant Agreement, strategies for engaging stakeholders identified as target groups will include:

- Open science actions
- Presentations at key conferences and events

- Direct engagement with professional societies of transplant medicine, kidney and liver research via briefings, journal contributions and website features
- Articles, interviews, and meetings with nephrology and liver disease patient groups
- Meetings with existing and potential industry partners, to explore collaboration on clinical trial and market access
- Ongoing public engagement via a comprehensive and active website and social media presence.

The strategic objective of the communication activities is to promote the project, engage the public, demonstrate the societal value of publicly funded research, and raise awareness (and hope) among transplant patients, their caregivers, and organisations.

Further, communication activity aims to raise awareness of the project in our scientific, clinical and industry communities, as a prelude to the dissemination and exploitation and dissemination of results.

3.6.1 Open Science Actions

By making project results and data accessible to all societal actors, other researchers, innovators and the public can find and re-use these for their own specific needs. In this way further research is encouraged, novel solutions can be found, and complex challenges can be tackled. This makes research outputs more transparent and their use more efficient. PHOENIX commits to open-access scientific publication and to publishing underlying data and protocols on Open Research Europe (ORE), European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) and Zenodo.

PHOENIX will target high-impact traditional publication venues and our research data will be published, FAIR-compliant, in open-access repositories (notably EOSC) using standard data formats and metadata. This will facilitate replication and validation of our work, minimise duplication of effort, and enable further analyses and potential further breakthroughs by other members of the scientific community.

Our objective is to transfer knowledge and results with the aim to enable others to use and take up our results, thus maximising the impact of EU-funded research. As outlined in the Grant Agreement, PHOENIX results will have exceptional commercialisation potential, such results will thus be protected, the approach to intellectual property is discussed further in section 3.1.8. below.

3.6.2 Presentations and Conferences

As per the Grant Agreement, initial conferences identified that align with the research of PHOENIX and provide an opportunity for a presentation are outlined below.

- ICIRII: International Conference on Immune Regulation, Immunotoxicology and Immunomicrobiology
- ICNDRM: International Conference on Nephrology Diagnosis and Renal Medicine
- ICCDMDR - International Conference on Cardiovascular, Diabetes, and Metabolic Disorders Research
- ICCN - International Congress of Nanoscience and Nanotechnology

Via the consultation survey, beneficiaries were asked to identify any additional conferences they are aware of to add to this list, after which a calendar of potential conferences will be continually updated via conference scanning conducted by WP5 and requests for potential conferences beneficiaries have

identified via the regular communication and dissemination reporting process (see section 3.1.10 Measures and Evaluations below).

3.6.3 Engagement - Professional Societies

As per the Grant Agreement, PHOENIX will engage (via for example events, briefings and social media) with professional societies in the fields of transplant medicine, kidney and liver research. The main societies that will initially be targeted include:

- ESOT: [European Society for Organ Transplants](#)
- ATC: [American Transplant Congress](#)
- ERA-EDTA: European Renal Association-European Dialysis and Transplant Association
- EASL: [European Association for the Study of Liver](#)

3.6.4 Engagement – Patient Groups

As per the Grant Agreement, PHOENIX will engage (via for example articles, interviews and meetings) with patient groups in the fields of nephrology and liver. The main patient groups in this field include:

- EKPF: [European Patient’s Kidney Foundation](#)
- CEAPIR: [European Patients’ Kidney Federation](#)
- ALCER: [National Federation of Associations ALCER \(Association for the Fight against Kidney Diseases\)](#)
- [FranceRein](#)
- ANED: Italian National Association of Emodialysis patients (ANED) and nephrology
- ELPA: [European Liver Patients Association](#)
- ASSCAT: [Catalonian Association of Liver Patients](#)

3.6.5 Engagement - Existing and Potential Industry Partners

These activities are discussed below in the exploitation section of the Initial Plan.

3.6.6 Engagement - General Public

The main channels through which the general public will be reached will be via the [PHOENIX website](#) and social media channels, namely: [Twitter](#) (@phoenix_nano), [LinkedIn](#) and [Facebook](#). As videos or animations explaining the project, methodology and results become available, these will be placed on a PHOENIX YouTube channel which will be established at that time.

To increase engagement, the websites and social media channels of beneficiaries will be leveraged. For example, PHOENIX Coordinators at IRFMN use Instagram (<https://www.instagram.com/istitutomarionegri/>) through which, to date, they promoted the mission and launch of the Project. To ensure website and social media content is fresh and engaging, PT will request via email on a two-weekly cycle any communication or dissemination activity from beneficiaries. This will also assist with continuous and periodic reporting. Herein, partners will be reminded to include the EU funding acknowledgement and disclaimer, and the open access publishing obligations.

3.7 Dissemination

The dissemination activities for the PHOENIX project are outlined in Task 5.3 – *Dissemination* of the Grant Agreement which as a task spans the duration of the project. As articulated in the Grant Agreement, the goal of dissemination is to raise awareness of the results and outcomes of the project, namely, the results determined in Task 4.2: *To identify lead candidate antigen (whether organ specific or ubiquitous) and the optimal MHC approach for clinical translation either in kidney or liver transplantation) during and after the project duration.*

Dissemination will emphasise end-results and re-usable outputs, targeting stakeholders best able to benefit from the PHOENIX results and outputs, namely:

- Scientific communities: via publications, shared data, new projects
- Industry: meetings to explore collaboration in taking results to the market
- Clinicians and patients: to maintain awareness and create market demand, via professional and mass-media publications, articles and online.

The strategic objective of our dissemination activities (during and after the project) is to promote the uptake and use of the project results. This includes:

- Paving the way to adoption of our nanotechnologies in clinical healthcare, to the benefit of patients and healthcare systems
- enabling further research in nanotechnology-enabled immunology
- creating awareness of, and demand for, the results, intellectual property and innovations created by PHOENIX.

3.7.1 Publications and Articles

Publications in peer-reviewed journals will be an important part of our dissemination strategy. We will use publications (in addition to conference presentations, as discussed in section 3.1.2) to reach academics, researchers, clinicians and other projects and initiatives. Specific journals also be used to target industry and policymakers. We will abide by the FAIR principles to disseminate our research findings as widely as possible. The author/researchers intended to provide guidelines to improve the Findability, Accessibility, Interoperability, and Reuse of digital assets. Publications will be posted to Zenodo, a free repository for open-access publications.

Via the consultation survey, partners were asked to identify target journals for PHOENIX (in addition to those in the Grant Agreement), this included:

- [Nano Letters](#)
- [Journal of Clinical Investigation](#)
- [Journal of Experimental Medicine](#)
- [Open Research Europe](#)

The PHOENIX consortium will also seek to leverage the many freely available tools of the Commission for online and printed publication opportunities (e.g., Horizon Magazine, Project Stories, etc.)

PHOENIX will also establish a Publication Policy which will uphold the following principles:

D5.2 Initial Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation Plan

- Publication is appropriately balanced against any requirement for intellectual property protection
- due consideration is given to the quality, order, timing and venue of publications, and
- unnecessary conflicts are avoided.

3.8 Exploitation

PHOENIX research itself represents a major step forward in the discovery and development of sophisticated approaches to the therapeutic manipulation of the immune system. PHOENIX researchers have already published their work on autoimmune diseases. PHOENIX jumps forward from this baseline, addressing the challenges of organ transplantation medicine and showcasing the potential for further applications of our discoveries in the reprogramming of the local immune system. This work will, in turn, provide the foundation for further breakthroughs, such as for example the potential application of this technology in xenotransplantation or in diseases with a pathogenic inflammatory component that is not strictly autoimmune in nature.

Herein is the opportunity to reduce the socioeconomic burden on healthcare systems. Treatment for transplant recipients of solid organs has a high cost for healthcare systems, including costs for hospitalization for complications/graft rejection and treatment, long-lasting immunosuppressive and other drugs.

The route to exploitation will be mapped out during the PHOENIX project and will benefit from insights and experience from our dedicated industry advisor, [Parvus Therapeutics](#). As stated in the Grant Agreement, our aim is for a small number of off-the-shelf therapeutics, effective for most transplant pairs.

Our most specific exploitation targets that play central roles in the long-term impact of the project are clinicians, research communities, healthcare providers/payers and future industry partners.

The exploitation activities in PHOENIX first relate to Task 5.4 – *Innovation Management* and then to Task 5.5 – *Exploitation Planning*.

3.8.1 Intellectual Property and Innovation Management

PHOENIX will develop and pre-clinically demonstrate revolutionary novel immunotherapies with immense innovation potential, high future market value and clinical/societal benefit.

As articulated in Task 5.4 – *Innovation Management*, discussions were held at the PHOENIX Kick-Off Meeting to as whether there were any existing innovations to be added to the Innovation Register. It was determined at this time that there was not, however, the process for managing innovation as outlined in the Grant Agreement would be a topic at the first Innovation Workshop (M6) which is to be held at the Plenary Meeting on 10 October 2023.

An IP review will take place at each plenary meeting. Ownership of intellectual property (IP) is fully covered in our Consortium Agreement (based on the DECSA model) and signed by all beneficiaries; the key points are as follows:

- (a) all Background IP will remain the sole property of its creator, both during and after the project
- (b) access to Background IP will be provided at no cost during the project, to allow all partners to deliver their roles in the project

(c) new Foreground (Results) IP will be the property of the inventing partner; where multiple partners are co-inventors, a joint ownership agreement will be agreed, enabling each to exploit the Foreground with fair and reasonable compensation to the co-inventor(s).

3.8.2 Potential Industry Partners

Meetings with existing and potential industry partners, to explore collaboration on clinical trial and market access will occur at the time when the research is sufficiently progressed. The identification of potential industry partners will be an agenda item at the first Innovation Workshop in M6.

3.8.3 Next steps for innovation – path to clinical trial

As outlined in the Grant Agreement, Task 5.5 - *Exploitation Planning* delivers the goal of the PHOENIX clinician scientists to deliver the technology underpinned by PHOENIX into the clinic as soon as possible. The Innovation Workshop organised by FCRB at Month 6 (and resulting in Deliverable 5.4 – *Initial Innovation Workshop Report*) in addition to what is discussed above, will establish a timeline, responsibilities, and roles for each innovation step, including:

- 1) up-scaling of NP and antigen production
- 2) GMP production and validation
- 3) further pre-clinical models
- 4) local and national ethics
- 5) regulatory approval
- 6) early-phase clinical trial preparation.

During the period M6-M18 we will hold meetings with Background IP holders at the University of Calgary and Parvus Therapeutics and agree a formal Materials Transfer Agreement that (a) ensures the academic freedom of all partners to publish PHOENIX Results, and (b) facilitates to the greatest degree possible the clinical translation of these Results.

A second Innovation Workshop will take place at Month 28 (to review and finalise the exploitation of all project Results), planning for this will be further detailed in the Updated Communications, Dissemination and Exploitation Plan (D5.4, due Month 18)

PHOENIX ends with the drafting of a Clinical Trial Protocol (led by IRFMN, Deliverable 4.3 due month 36) for the first-in-human Phase 1 clinical trial of the PHOENIX output which performs best in our studies (organ-specific or universal pMHCII- and/or α GalCer/CD1d-based).

3.9 Measures and Evaluations

As detailed above, we will track and record communication, dissemination, and exploitation activities by circulating requests for updates to all partners at regular intervals. Details of all activities will then be collated by PT and entered on the Project's Communication and Dissemination Register (maintained by PT). This Register will ultimately be used for drafting project reports, including the continuous reporting module. We aim to publish one news item per month on the website.

Additional metrics will also be used to track progress for some specific forms of communication and dissemination e.g., analytics tools for the website via Google Analytics, user data for social media accounts. We will continuously monitor our progress and metrics to identify successful (and unsuccessful) activities. In addition, ahead of the release of D5.4 (Updated Communications,

Dissemination and Exploitation Plan), we will conduct a short feedback survey of beneficiaries and an internal review of the Initial Plan, adjusting it as required.

Progress will be reported to the EU in our periodic reports at months 18 and 36 and in our final report and via the continuous reporting on communication and dissemination in SyGMA.

In terms of exploitation, key activities will be reported via the two deliverables related to the Innovation Workshops: D5.7 – *Initial Innovation Workshop Report* (due Month 8) D5.8 – *Final Innovation Workshop Report* (due Month 29) and D5.6 – *Final Exploitation Plan* (due Month 30).

4. Results

The results of the approach taken as outlined in Section 3 of this report is the Initial Plan, the main components of which are outlined in turn below.

4.1 Communication and Dissemination Plan

To address the communication and dissemination objectives, we devised a strategy whereby each audience is targeted through an array of channels with distinct messages. The Initial Plan for communication and dissemination activities by type are articulated in Table 1, below.

Table 1: Initial Communication and Dissemination plan and metrics to measure impact

Target Audience	Channels	Key Messages	Measurement of Progress and Impact (# = 'number of')
General Public	Website, slide, social media, promotional materials, press release, explainer video	<p>This exciting new science aims to help improve the quality of life for those who need an organ transplant.</p> <p>There is societal value in this publicly-funded research.</p> <p>Health burden of chronic diseases is reduced.</p> <p>Rates of graft loss and patient death are too high – PHOENIX is addressing this issue.</p> <p>Through the project mission and its value to society as a whole, PHOENIX represents public money well-spent: Advancing research into immuno-nanomedicines.</p>	<p>#social media posts</p> <p>#articles in popular press</p> <p>#unique visitors to the website</p> <p>#social media followers</p> <p>#subscribers</p> <p>#video views</p>
Transplant patients and carers	Website, slide, events, social media, promotional materials, press release, explainer video	<p>Premature mortality from non-communicable diseases can be reduced.</p> <p>Reduced need for second transplants due to graft loss, means more organs available for transplantation.</p> <p>The new nanomedicine may reduce the need for long-term immunosuppressive and other post-transplant medicines.</p>	<p>#seminars and workshops</p> <p>#subscribers</p> <p>#video views</p> <p>#articles in periodicals and websites of patient organisations</p> <p>#subscribers</p> <p>#video views</p>

Target Audience	Channels	Key Messages	Measurement of Progress and Impact (# = 'number of')
Academic and industrial research communities	Website, Publications, social media, Conference presentations, medical magazines, networking events	<p>PHOENIX’s novel immuno-nanomedicine offers a new window into immunology and pre-clinical research in transplant medicine, which can be utilised in drug development and testing contexts.</p> <p>Openly sharing scientific methodologies and knowledge will enable advancements in research and innovation that build upon PHOENIX findings.</p> <p>This breakthrough research has immense healthcare and patient benefit potential.</p> <p>Building on recent success and innovation, PHOENIX has a foundation of robust evidence of efficacy.</p>	<p>#scientific publications and citations</p> <p>#participants to project events</p> <p>#conference presentations</p>
Other research projects	Website links, social media, Conferences	We are using cutting edge research approaches and are committed to open science and further collaborations.	
Clinical transplant community	Website, Publications, social media, Conference presentations, medical magazines, networking events	<p>PHOENIX is creating state-of-the-art tools to improve patient care and outcomes.</p> <p>Our novel transplant medicines can revolutionise the field.</p> <p>Current healthcare costs are too high. We can do better.</p> <p>We will be human trial ready in 2026.</p> <p>Pandemics present additional risks to immune-compromised patients.</p>	<p>#participants to workshops</p> <p>#attended conferences</p> <p>#articles in journals and websites of professional bodies</p>
Industry and business community	Website, Conferences, promotional materials, Industry magazines, Publications, social media	<p>New emerging nano technologies present unique opportunities in drug development.</p> <p>Current healthcare costs are too high. Partner with PHOENIX and engage with our new approaches, we can do better.</p>	<p>#contact with industries network</p> <p>#partnerships in new R&I initiatives</p>

4.2 Branding, Logo and Website

The PHOENIX logo and colour scheme are provided below. The logo depicts a modern, sleek phoenix in gold, grey and black, with tail feathers merging into a geometric circle, symbolising unity, and collaboration. This logo reflects the transformative impact on patients’ lives and organ transplantation, as a whole. For further details on the branding and logo, please refer to the D5.1 report. The website will serve as the nerve centre for communications and will document the mission, progress and results of the project each step of the way.

Figure 1 – PHOENIX Logo

Figure 1 – PHOENIX Colour Scheme

As detailed in D5.1, the PHOENIX website will enable communication about, create interest in, and demand for, our research outputs within the medical and research and development communities. This will ultimately support exploitation planning (Task 5.5).

Figure 3 – PHOENIX Project Website

4.3 Communication and Dissemination Toolkit

In line with the Grant Agreement and results of the beneficiary consultation survey, WP5 will develop the following products for the communication and dissemination toolkit:

- Press release for launch
- Project flyer
- Professional illustrations
- Videos explaining the project
- PHOENIX in one slide – for project promotion
- PHOENIX Visual Abstract – communicating the project methodology
- Interviews with team members

These tools will be designed to help the general public and interested non-specialists visualise our work and make complex information attractive and more accessible for a lay audience.

4.4 Leveraging beneficiary networks

We have connections to other researchers and project teams to stimulate further research both through face-to-face networking at conferences, training events, and in-house institutional seminars and digitally through social media and web links.

PHOENIX PIs are experts in their fields and will use their well-established links to contacts, networks, and patient organisations such as *Fondazione Trapianti* to spread the news of the project aims and results. We plan to use existing resources in our consortium to increase outreach on international, national, and regional level. To a certain extent, we will rely on our project partners' communication departments, and involve our consortium's innovation experts who may will experience in this domain.

4.5 Interaction with Sister Projects

We will contact via email the eight projects funded under the European Commission call (sister projects, Table 2 below) in order to connect via social media and explore ways to work together to

D5.2 Initial Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation Plan

amplify key messages, and complement one another's work surrounding the benefits of using of public funding for the research and development into the next-generation of therapies to improve the health and lives of EU citizens with unmet medical needs.

An increased awareness of EU-funded research and innovation activities and project results will directly and indirectly provide many benefits, such as helping secure or increase research and innovation funding, establishing new research or business contacts, and stimulating further research.

Table 2: Horizon Europe-funded Sister Projects

SISTER PROJECTS	Project acronym, URL, if available
Preclinical development of a 3rd-generation interleukin-2 targeted to inflammatory sites	TiIT
Autoantigen-specific adoptive regulatory T cell therapy against type 1 diabetes	ARTiDe
Novel immunotherapies for tuberculosis and other mycobacterial diseases	ITHEMYC
Validation of novel immunotherapeutic targets against fibrosis in inflammatory bowel diseases	FIBROTARG; https://fibrotarget.eu/
Gut Microbiota-Induced Tregs for Inflammatory-Bowel-Disease (IBD) Immunotherapy	MITI 2
Therapeutic Epigenetic Enhancement of the Innate Immunity to Effectively Combat Antimicrobial Resistance	IN-ARMOR
Advanced Antigen-specific Dendritic Cell-based Therapy to Re-establish Tolerance in Immune-Mediated Diseases	IMMUTOL; https://immunol-horizon.eu/
Next Generation Vaccine Platform Leveraging Skin Immunity to Provide Disease-Modifying Treatment of Parkinson's Disease	NEXGEN-PD; https://www.nexgen-pd.eu/

4.6 Exploitation Plan

At each plenary meeting, we will raise awareness among all partners concerning good research practice and the importance of IP management (incl. confidentiality, ownership, access rights, responsibilities). Through IP reviews and a Publication Policy, we will establish procedure to assess, balance and moderate the possibly varying exploitation interests of project partners. This will be the foundation for an all-partner federated strategy that responds to the general objective of the project to jointly address the specific EU call's challenges and its expected impacts. This will set up proper arrangements to ensure that legitimate interests of project partners will not be compromised. In addition, it will allow partners to systematically plan, prepare and implement appropriate activities to identify, assess and prioritise key exploitable results, such as- follow-up research, study designs, IP rights, products and services.

Through our two planned innovation workshops, invited and internal experts will employ strategic intelligence to identify and assess competing technologies, competitors, future trends, clinical trial preparation, future funding targets and potential publications. Our DoA describes how the project results will be accessed and used for further related research and clinical trial readiness, with well-defined expected terms of use.

5. Impact and Conclusion

Communication, dissemination and exploitation are key to the success of PHOENIX. It takes an integrated approach to effectively carry out communication, dissemination and exploitation activities. Our Initial Plan enables us to capture and monitor project results, select the right tools to inform about them, and manage open access while at the same time considering a strategy for IP protection. We have well-established procedures to recognise, capture and characterise project outputs.

This report articulates the Initial Communication, dissemination and Exploitation Plan for PHOENIX and provides details of the activities planned. In it, we set well defined goals, chosen our audiences, crafted our messages and identified adequate communication tools and channels. We plan to highlight the benefits of PHOENIX for society and leverage the existing resources in our consortium.

Effective dissemination will increase the visibility of the project in target groups, thereby maximising the influence and impact of our work. Dissemination will be a continuous process throughout the project as results are obtained and will create a favourable ground for exploitation after PHOENIX ends. We have supports in place to document and demonstrate our communication activities and outcomes for periodic reports.

This Initial Plan promotes PHOENIX on many levels, reaching out to both a wider audience and interested parties, while exploring possible exploitation routes. We will monitor and constantly update the communication strategy and activity plan by examining what lessons have been learned and/or what could be improved. This Initial Plan will be reviewed and revised ahead of M18.

6. Appendices

Researchers' Online Consultation Survey

PHOENIX Communication and Dissemination Partner Survey

Dear PHOENIX Partners,

As the experts in PHOENIX you know your scientific networks and communities best.

We seek your input to the Initial Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation Plan so that we are best positioned to communicate and disseminate your good work!

This survey should not take longer than 10 minutes to complete.

The results will only be used for internal purposes.

We look forward to your feedback and if you have any questions please contact us.

Best wishes - Ainslie & Danielle

ainslie.oconnor@pintailservices.com
danielle.nicholson@pintailservices.com

* Required

1

Name *

2

Organisation *

3

We have drafted key messages for each target audience, are you satisfied with these? *

Target Audience	Key Messages
General Public	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> This exciting new science aims to improve the quality of life for those who need an organ transplant. There is societal value in this publicly funded research. Health burden of chronic diseases is reduced. Rates of graft loss and patient death are too high - PHOENIX is addressing this issue. Through the project mission and its value to society, PHOENIX represents public money well-spent: Advancing research into immuno-nanomedicines.
Transplant patients and carers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Premature mortality from non-communicable diseases can be reduced. Reduced need for second transplants due to graft loss, means more organs available for transplantation. The new nanomedicine may reduce the need for long-term immunosuppressive and other post-transplant medicines.
Academic and industrial research communities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> PHOENIX's novel immuno-nanomedicine offers a new window into immunology and pre-clinical research in transplant medicine, which can be utilised in drug development and testing contexts. Openly sharing scientific methodologies and knowledge will enable advancements in research and innovation that build upon PHOENIX findings. This breakthrough research has immense healthcare and patient benefit potential. Building on recent success and innovation, PHOENIX has a foundation of robust evidence of efficacy.
Other research projects	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> We are using cutting edge research approaches and are committed to open science and further collaborations.
Clinical transplant community	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> PHOENIX is creating state-of-the-art tools to improve patient care and outcomes. Our novel transplant medicines can revolutionize the field. Current healthcare costs are too high. We can do better. We will be human trial ready in 2026. Pandemics present additional risks to immune-compromised patients.
Industry and business community	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> New emerging nano technologies present unique opportunities in drug development. Current healthcare costs are too high; partner with PHOENIX and engage with our new approaches, together we can do better.

Yes

No

4

Please outline below which key messages you would adapt, remove or add.

5

Please select the item(s) you would find most useful in the PHOENIX Communication and Dissemination Toolkit. *

- Press Release Template
- Project Flyer
- Professional illustrations (to describe the project or results)
- Videos and animations explaining the project
- PHOENIX in one slide – for project promotion
- PHOENIX Visual Abstract – communicating the project methodology
- Interviews with team members (for web and social media promotion)
- Pull up banner
- Other

6

The PHOENIX proposal listed the following conferences, please list below others we should target.

- **ICIRII** - International Conference on Immune Regulation, Immunotoxicology and Immunomicrobiology
- **ICNDRM** - International Conference on Nephrology Diagnosis and Renal Medicine
- **ICDMDR** - International Conference on Cardiovascular, Diabetes, and Metabolic Disorders Research
- **ICCN** - International Congress on Nanoscience and Nanotechnology

7

Please select which (if any) of the following societies you are a member. *

- ESOT**: European Society for Organ Transplants
- ATC**: American Transplant Congress
- RA-EDTA**: European Renal Association-European Dialysis and Transplant Association
- EASL**: European Association for the Study of Liver
- None of the above

8

Are you a member of any other professional societies linked to the work of PHOENIX?

- Yes
- No

9

Which professional society/societies?

10

Please select which (if any) of the following patient groups you are linked to. *

- EKPF:** European Patient's Kidney Foundation
- CEAPIR:** European Patients' Kidney Federation
- ALCER:** National Federation of Associations ALCER (Association for the Fight against Kidney Diseases)
- FranceRein**
- ANED:** Italian National Association of Emodialysis patients (ANED) and nephrology
- ELPA:** European Liver Patients Association
- ASSCAT:** Catalanian Association of Liver Patients
- None of the above

11

Are you linked to any other patient groups relevant to PHOENIX?

- Yes
- No

12

Which patient groups?

13

Please list any other scientific events (e.g., open days, science festivals), networks or organisations that present communication and dissemination opportunities for PHOENIX that you would like WP5 to explore.

14

In what ways can you contribute to the communication of PHOENIX to the general public and patient community?

- Write piece about PHOENIX (and your related research) for a patient newsletter/website
- Participate in a public event- local science festival, patient group meeting, institutional Open Day, World Kidney Day, etc.
- Contribute to a hospital 'Awareness Day' campaign via social media
- Make a short video about your group's work within PHOENIX to be shared on the website and social media
- Other

15

The following journals were listed in the proposal as targets for PHOENIX publications, please list below others we should target.

- Nano Letters
- Journal of Clinical Investigation
- Journal of Experimental Medicine
- Open Research Europe

16

Please provide the name and email address of the best contact person (for Pintail to contact) for communication and dissemination activities (including events and media) in your organisation.

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